

DEVELOPMENT HIGH TEMPERATURE RESISTANT MATERIALS USING CARBON/PHENOLIC PREPREGS WITH NANOCCLAYS

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1 General Introduction

Fiber reinforced polymers have emerged as a major class of structural materials and are either used or being considered for use as substitution for metals in many weight-critical components in aerospace, automotive, and other industries [1].

In the specific case of aerospace industry, the materials used must meet additional requirements such as dimensional stability, high stiffness and high temperature resistance. Fire resistance and ablative composites are used in nozzle turbine construction and other components of rockets and airplane engines, exposed to very high temperatures. Phenolic resin/Carbon fiber reinforced composites are indicated for these applications due to its high mechanical and thermal performance. Phenolic resins (in particular the resol type) are obtained when the reaction between phenol and formaldehyde is carried out in basic conditions and with formaldehyde excess. One of the most important properties of these resins is their excellent flame and high temperatures resistance, which is due to the formation of a carbonaceous layer called "char" that radiates heat and acts as an insulating material, protecting the bulk material of the components [2]. Nowadays phenolic resins are used in thermal protection systems, molding compounds, wood products, coatings, and different types of composite materials [3]. Regarding carbon fibers, they have been widely used as reinforcement in composites for thermal protection due to its high dimensional stability, non-flammability, low density and excellent mechanical properties [4]. Composite materials based on phenolic resins and carbon fibers have being used for NASA as standard material for high temperature applications (MX-4926). This material has also micron-sized powdered fillers in the formulation, which is added in order to stabilize the charred polymer that can be mechanically removed by the friction action caused by the

atmospheric gases during the combustion. Particles based on glass, refractory oxides, carbon or mineral asbestos are typically used. But traditional micron-sized ablation composites have shown a threshold in their protection capacity that cannot be surpassed unless a different approach is proposed. One of the limitations comes from the fact that chars are structurally weak and suffer mechanical erosion, reducing the lifetime of the ablative layer or requiring additional insulation thickness. Also, the composite-like nature of these ablatives severely limits their processibility and requires them to be pattern cut, and laid into place by hand [5]. Materials with better ablative properties would permit applying relatively thinner protection layers, reducing the overall weight of aerospace systems. Thermoset polymer nanocomposites have excellent potential as ablative materials because upon pyrolysis, the organic-inorganic nanostructure reinforcing the polymer can be converted into a uniform ceramic layer which may lead to significantly increased resistance to oxidation and mechanical erosion compared to traditional composite ablative materials [6]. Different nanoparticles have in used with phenolic resins in order to enhance its ablation and thermal resistance. Srikanth et al. [7] added nanosilica particles to carbon-phenolic composites and obtained much higher ablation resistance than conventional carbon-phenolic materials under similar conditions. They attributed this behavior to the reaction of the nanosilica with char at high-temperature, forming ablation resistant silicon carbide phase. Natali et al. [8] studied the ablative properties of highly loaded carbon black and MWCNT/phenolic composites. They found that MWNT-based system showed a thin charred region whilst the Carbon black system was characterized by a thick and wide pyrolyzed zone, which effectively shielded the virgin material. Also nano-layered silicates have being used in phenolic-

carbon composites to improve its thermal properties. Koo et al. [9] made carbon/phenolic composites with different clay loads (2.5, 5 and 7.5%). It was found that only high loaded materials (7.5% of nanoclays) produced a reduction in erosion rate, the surface temperature and in the maximum backside heat-soaked temperature rise. When comparing different nanoparticles, nanoclays have the advantage of being cheaper, abundant, and relatively easy to modify chemically in order to make them more compatible with the polymer matrix.

Regarding the processing techniques, in aerospace applications, besides thermal resistance, is important to have high mechanical performance. The manufacturing technique that ensures the best mechanical properties is the autoclave processing, which allows obtaining composite with low porosity and high fiber content [10]. The raw materials for processing by autoclave are prepregs, which facilitate placing resin and fibers in the necessary amount in the mold. Therefore, if a new ablative material is developed, is important to know how prepregs manufacturing and application are affected by the presence of nanoclays. But in the scientific literature, few works can be found addressing the issue of prepregs obtaining process and its main variables [11, 12].

The aim of this work is to obtain and to characterize phenolic resin/carbon fiber- prepregs and its composites, which can be used in the aerospace industry. Nanoclays (bentonites) were chemically modified and added to phenolic resin in order to evaluate their effect on the performance of the material. Cone calorimeter fire properties of the composites were studied.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The resol-type phenolic resin was prepared using formaldehyde: phenol molar ratio equal to 1:3 [3] under basic conditions. Phenol and formaldehyde water solution (37 wt.%) was placed in a 1 l stainless steel reactor with a low velocity stirrer, a thermometer and reflux condenser. The pH was kept at 9.0 with a solution of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) 40 wt.% and the mixture was allowed to react for 2 h at 90 °C. After that, the mixture was neutralized with a solution of boric acid until the pH reached a value of 6.8-7.0. The dehydration of the resol was performed in a rotary evaporator by vacuum at 75 °C.

The obtained resin was kept at -10 °C until it was used. Phenol and formaldehyde used for the synthesis were supplied by Cicarelli. Modified phenolic resin was obtained by adding 5 % w/w of ammonium modified bentonite to the original resol; the method used to modify the clay, by cation exchange reaction, is explained elsewhere [13]. Bentonite was supplied by Minarmco S.A. Carbon fiber fabric (Toray T700SC-12000), supplied by Yixing Huaheng High Performance Fiber Textile CO, was used as reinforcement.

2.2 Resin and clay characterization

Curing Kinetics. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra of the resol were obtained in transmission mode using a Nicolet 6700 spectrometer, in the range of 600 to 4000 cm⁻¹. The spectra was normalized using the band at 1595 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the stretching C=C of the benzene ring that was expected to remain constant in all the samples.

Viscosity measurements. Measurements were performed in a Brookfield cone and plate viscometer HBTDV-IICP at room temperature.

Gel Time. Measurements were performed with test tubes in a controlled temperature bath at 80, 100 and 120 °C.

Clay characterization. X Ray Diffraction (XRD) spectra were obtained in a Panalytical X PERT PRO spectrometer, with CuK α ($\lambda=1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) radiation at room temperature. The generator voltage was 40 kV and the current was 40 mA. Thermogravimetric tests were carried out in a TGA-DTGA Shimadzu 50, from room temperature to 1000 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in nitrogen atmosphere.

2.3 Prepregs and composite preparation

Phenolic resin-unidirectional stitched carbon fiber prepregs (PC), and phenolic resin with 5 wt.% of bentonite-unidirectional stitched carbon fiber prepregs (PBC) were obtained for composite preparation. Prepregs were obtained by vacuum bag molding which consists in six steps: mold preparation, fabric cutting, impregnation, bag application, curing and demolding. First, the mold was cleaned and a release agent (REN RP79-2) was applied in order to facilitate the demolding step. The release agent is needed due to the fact that the prepreg usually adhere to the mold after curing. Then, the fibers, bleeder fabric, release film and the

vacuum bag were cut. Once all materials were prepared, the carbon fabric was manually impregnated with phenolic resin. After the impregnation, the release film and the bleeder fabric were placed over the fibers and then the vacuum bag was sealed along the perimeter of the fabric area. The curing took place in oven for 4 h at 80 °C. The vacuum was applied during the first 2 hours.

Composite materials were obtained by compression molding of prepregs in a heated press. Laminates were cut in 10 cm x12 cm rectangles, and staked in the same direction into a steel mold with release agent. The thermal curing cycle was: 15 min at 45°C, 1 h at 60°C, 4 h at 80°C, 1 h at 110°C, 1 h at 150°C and 2 h at 190°C. 1 Ton of pressure was applied throughout the cycle.

2.4 Prepregs and composite characterization

- Prepregs flexural rigidity tests: Tests were performed at room temperature in a universal testing machine Instron 4467, according to ASTM D1388, procedure A.

- Prepreg tack testing: Prepregs tack was measured at room temperature according to ASTM D3167 standard, in a universal testing machine Instron 4467.

- Composites flexural properties: Tests were performed in a universal testing machine Instron 4467 with a 30 kN load cell, according to ASTM D790 standard.

- Composites fire resistance: Composite materials were tested in a Fire Testing Technology cone calorimeter with ConeCalc software. The heat release rate (HRR), total heat release (THR), time to ignition and time of the HRR peak were obtained according to ASTM E1354. The samples were tested in horizontal configuration. The radiant heat flux was 50 kW/m²; the specimen has an exposed surface area of 0.010 m² (100 mm x 100 mm). The thickness of the specimen was 4 mm approximately.

3 Results

3.1. Characterization of modified clay

Figure 1 shows the original and modified bentonite XRD spectra with their respective interlaminar spacing. It can be observed that modified bentonite presents a displacement of the 001 peak to a lower angle of incidence and, therefore, an increase in the interlayer distance as compared to the original clay.

Furthermore it can be seen a single diffraction peak, which indicates a uniform spacing.

Regarding to thermogravimetric test, the mass loss curve as a function of temperature and DTG curve (Figure 2) of the unmodified bentonite show two thermal degradation transitions: a) the surface adsorbed water which volatilizes at low temperatures and b) crystallization water which does at higher temperatures. In the case of modified bentonites, in general four regions of mass loss can be distinguished: a) the evolution of water and gaseous species physically adsorbed (below 150 °C); b) the organic substances decomposition (between 150 and 550 °C), c) the dehydroxylation of the bentonite by loss of structural water (between 550 and 750 °C) and d) the evolution of organic carbonaceous products (between 700 and 800 °C). Both results demonstrated that the clay was successfully modified and that its interlaminar space was expanded and, observing the disappearance of water peak, that the modified bentonite is more hydrophobic than the original one.

Ones modified bentonite was obtained, it was added to the resin in a proportion of 5 wt.%. The resin was previously dehydrated during different times until a viscosity that facilitates the clay dispersion was achieved (1100 cP). Clay was added gradually with continuous stirring, and after obtaining a homogeneous mixture it was sonicated for 30 minutes in an ultrasonic bath to ensure a good dispersion.

The FTIR spectra of matrix obtained at different temperatures were analyzed based on the methylene bridges bands, appearing at 1456 and 1473 cm⁻¹, for the “para – para” and “ortho-para” bridges respectively. The maximum of the reaction was reached after 20 minutes at 190 °C. With this data and the spectrum obtained after 4 h at 80 °C, it was concluded that prepregs obtained has 35% conversion, as it can be seen in Figure 3. The resin kinetics characterization was made by using Eq. 1 for the spectra obtained after a dynamic test, and Eq. 2 for the spectra obtained after a constant temperature (isothermal) test.

$$\alpha_T = H_T / H_{max} \quad (2)$$

were, α_T is conversion to a certain temperature, H_T is peak height and H_{max} is the maximum peak height.

$$\alpha_t = (H_{T,t} / H_{T_{t=0}}) * \alpha_{max.T} \quad (3)$$

were α_t is conversion to a certain time, $H_{T,t}$ is peak height at a certain time, $H_{T_{t=0}}$ is peak height at initial time, and $\alpha_{max.T}$ is conversion obtained by Eq. 1. Gel times obtained for unmodified and modified phenolic resin as a function of temperature are presented in Table 1. It can be observed that phenolic resin does not reach the gel time during the first 4 h at 80°C, this is the reason why processing cycle (temperature and time) used was selected.

Figure 4 shows the obtained prepregs; their dimensions were 45 cm x 35 cm. The properties of the obtained in the characterization tests are summarized in Table 2. It can be seen that the only property that was significantly affected by nanoclays incorporation is the degree of tack. Certain tack is required to facilitate the placement of the layers before autoclave processing, but it should not be too high so that when a ply is misplaced during the lay-up process it cannot be readily relocated. The tack of unmodified prepregs could not be measured because they did not adhere to the device that was used for the measurement. The tack of modified prepregs was in the order of commercial prepregs, and the increase in its value is attributed to the increasing viscosity of the matrix, caused by the addition of clay to resin.

Physical and mechanical properties of composites manufactured with the prepregs are summarized in Table 3. The modified composite material showed significant lower resistance and modulus. The drop of the mechanical properties when adding nanoclays to the phenolic resin can be explained by the lower fiber content that is achieved during composite manufacturing. The difference in the final fiber content is due to the higher viscosity of the modified phenolic resin, which reduces the resin extraction of the bleeder during the processing. The obtained values for the unmodified phenolic composite are in the range of values that can be obtained for typical epoxy-carbon composites ("Ref" in Table 2, [14])

In terms of fire resistance, characteristic times are presented in Figure 5. Longer ignition times (tig) and shorter flame duration (t flame) are desirable for improving the fire performance of the materials. Also, it is better to delay the time for which the maximum heat release rate is achieved (tHRR). It

can be seen that both phenolic composites have longer ignition times than a carbon-epoxy composite used as reference [15]. At the same time, the addition of bentonite increased the flame duration but had a positive effect by increasing the time of HRR peak of the phenolic composites.

Regarding the heat parameters, it can be observed in Figure 6 that HRR peak is lower for the bentonite modified composite, than for the original one. Higher values of the HRR peak are detrimental for the fire performance, since it is an indication of higher velocities of fire spreading. The peak of HRR was much lower than the observed for traditional epoxy-carbon composites. Also, the total heat evolved (THR) during the combustion was considerably lower for the phenolic composites (Table 4). Another important parameter is the residual mass of the composites after fire. In general, higher residual mass is an indication of better mechanical integrity of the burned materials. Phenolic composites showed residual mass higher than 80%. If the fiber content is considered (82% for PC and 73% for PBC), the amount of residual mass corresponding to the matrix is higher in the bentonite modified composite. It is believed that the clay promotes the formation of a char that insulates the material, preventing the total burning of the composite. Figure 7 shows the samples during and after cone calorimeter tests. It can be seen that in samples without clay (in the left) the aluminum foil that is putted in the back side of the samples was melted, but it remained intact in the composite modified with bentonite. That behavior is related to the stabilization of the insulation layer by the nanoclay particles in the matrix.

Parameters related to smoke emission worse with the addition of bentonite to the polymer matrix, as shown in Table 5. Nevertheless, these parameters are important in the case of materials used in the construction industry or for structural parts of the fuselage in commercial aircrafts, but not for composites used in rockets or plane turbines.

4 Conclusions

Phenolic resin-carbon fiber prepregs could be obtained and characterized. Also, the effect to adding nanoclays to the phenolic resin was studied. The degree of tack was increased with the addition of bentonite and the fiber volume fraction achieved

in the final composite was reduced. These effects were attributed to the increase in the viscosity of the phenolic resin.

Regarding the composite materials, the addition of clay was detrimental for the mechanical properties of the phenolic based materials, while improved some fire properties such as the peak of the heat release rate and the residual mass of the burned samples. Also, the bentonite modified composited required higher time to develop the maximum of the Heat Release Rate in the material.

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6 Figures and Tables

Fig.1 - XRD spectra of modified and unmodified bentonite

Fig. 2 – TGA and DTG curves of modified and unmodified bentonite

Fig. 3-a) conversion vs. temperature, and b) conversion vs. time obtained curves.

Fig. 4. Photograph of a) unmodified prepreg and b) modified prepreg.

Fig. 5. Characteristic times of different materials under fire.

DEVELOPMENT HIGH TEMPERATURE RESISTANT PREPREGS USING CARBON/PHENOLIC PREPREGS WITH NANOCLEYS

Fig. 6. HRR evolution as a function of time for the two materials studied

Fig. 7. Samples during and after cone calorimeter tests

Tab. 1. Gel time of original and modified phenolic resin as a function of temperature

Temperature (°C)	Phenolic resin gel time	Modified Phenolic resin gel time
80	More than 4 h	More than 4 h
100	2 h 57 min	2 h 5 min
120	41 min	34 min

Tab. 2. Prepregs fiber content and density

Property	Unmodified Prepregs	Modified Prepregs
Density (g/ml)	1.01 ± 0.19	1.26 ± 0.10
Fiber content (volume %)	43 ± 8	45 ± 4
Stiffness (mJ/m)	18.5 ± 6,0	13.8 ± 2.8
Tack (N/m)	-	4.4 ± 0.79

Tab. 3. Flexural test results

Property	PC	PBC
Fiber content (vol %)	82±1	73±4
Density	1.60 ± 0.04	1.70 ± 0.02
Flexural modulus (GPa)	130±7	104±6
Flexural Streght (GPa)	1.0±0.7	0.68±0.09

Tab. 4. Cone calorimeter results

Property	PC	PBC	Ref
pHRR (kW/m ²)	111.0	86.1	347.0
THR (MJ/m ²)	16.7	15.9	26.2
Residue (%)	88.2	83.8	72.8

Tab. 5. Total smoke production and smoke production rate for both materials.

Material	TSP (m ²)	SPR (m ² /s)
PC	0.9	0.0017
PBC	2.4	0.0040